

Impact of Apple's branding on financial performance

To what extent has Apple's branding affected their financial performance in the smartphone market?

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Introduction

Apple Inc., founded in 1976 as a small tech startup, has since grown to become the most valuable company and brand in the world with a market capitalisation of \$3 trillion (Linzmayr, 2024). **Branding** is a uniquely identifying marketing technique for companies with four aspects: awareness, loyalty, development, and value. Branding is so important for Apple that it completely defines their identity and due to the competitive nature of the technology industry and the smartphone market, gives them the ability to differentiate themselves for financial performance. This essay will explore the extent to which **Apple's branding affects its financial performance in the smartphone market.**

Methodology

Sources

This research uses secondary data such as smartphone market analyses and Apple's annual reports to evaluate and establish the link between Apple's branding and financial performance. Due to Apple's global influence, it is one of the world's most documented and studied corporations. However, this abundance of data also raises concerns about the validity of some that aren't directly verifiable; therefore, there will be some margin of error and subjectivity in data collection that isn't accurate or published by Apple Inc.

Tools and Theories

The different aspects of branding will be investigated using distinct tools and theories. Keller's brand equity model helps categorise different levels of connection between the brand and the market to create an approach to improve perceptions, values, and feelings. These subcategories are indicators and contributors of brand awareness; however, data to support

these categories and link to their consequences, such as customer satisfaction to sales revenue and pricing power, are necessary.

Social Identity Theory is the basis of consumer behaviour and loyalty, which explains whether branding efforts result in financial success. Brand loyalty is analysed by comparing it to the social identity theory and its indicators, such as ingroup favouritism and self-esteem with its financial effect on customers such as retention and customer lifetime value (CLV).

The Brand Value Chain is a framework that constructs the value stages of brand development and its consequent brand value. It is used to understand the effects of strategic investment and competitive actions on financial performance.

Limitations

Due to branding's intangible and subjective nature, there will be inherent bias in the data used to explain it. This investigation seeks to eliminate subjectivity and identify facts through the triangulation of multiple sources, establishing more reliable analysis and connections between data. There are also limitations of the tools and theories.

Keller's Brand Equity Model only categorises the success regarding branding and does not establish any connections with financial performance; however, this essay aims to link the two areas together by employing other tools and data.

Similarly, Social Identity Theory is a psychological, consumer-centric theory that doesn't directly identify the effects of branding on financial success. Additionally, indicators such as ingroup favouritism and self-esteem aren't quantifiable; therefore, this essay requires quantitative data to establish objective reasoning and conclusions.

The Brand Value Chain requires the quantification of intangible assets, but these factors are interconnected and interdependent, resulting in subjectivity in valuation and assessment.

Brand awareness

Brand awareness is the extent to which customers know, recognise, remember and relate to a brand. Keller's Customer-Based Brand Equity Model is a guide that categorises brand-building and market research strategies into different levels of intensity. The analysis begins from the bottom of the pyramid, which represents the most basic form of awareness, upwards to passionate relationships.

Figure 1: Keller's Customer-Based Brand Equity Model (Hawker)

Brand salience is the measure of how quickly a brand comes to mind when a consumer considers purchasing a product or service (Mchunu, 2023).

Figure 2: UK Apple brand survey (Kunst, 2024)

Figure 2 represents the data of a brand survey done on the UK's consumer electronics users for Apple. As visible in Figure 2, in 2023, 93% of >1000 respondents were aware of Apple, which highlights success in creating salience in a trillion-dollar market for broad exposure, familiarity and high likelihood for purchases. Apple achieved this through large-scale marketing campaigns like 'Think Different' and 'Shot on iPhone', which inspire people and make them aware of the innovative brand culture, communicating their values to simultaneously increase popularity. Due to the majority of the market being aware of Apple, their marketing and customer acquisition costs could be very low; however, there is no explicit data to confirm this. A very high level of awareness does not guarantee sales and a positive reputation; as the general population already knows the brand, advertising would be useful for increasing popularity from the 44% of people who already know the brand up to the 93% aware, rather than introducing it to the 7% unfamiliar, for more financial efficiency (Statista, 2024). This marketing and branding approach persuades the viewers who may not be completely convinced through ethos and pathos as it provides evidence of the iPhone's capabilities and evokes optimism, consequently, improving brand judgments to make customers more passionate, which increases sales revenue and CLV.

Furthermore, Apple promotes its premium brand to the general public, increasing exposure, awareness and sales through its stores with futuristic architecture in prime locations. These stores are carefully designed for emotional customer engagement, providing unique selling points (USPs) and sales experiences to increase awareness and positive brand perceptions for more sales revenue. The estimated average cost of these stores is \$10 million and therefore, would reduce profitability ratios; however, this would be a long-term investment into a continuous promotional asset, reducing Apple's revenue expenditure for publicity for enhanced long-term financial sustainability (Rosoff, 2021).

Brand performance is the extent to which a brand and its products meet its consumers' needs and expectations (MindTools, 2024). **Brand imagery** focuses on the brand's ability to meet consumers' psychological and social needs, shaping how the brand is perceived (Mchunu, 2023).

Apple's development of a minimalistic yet well-designed user interface for their products contributes to strong brand performance as customers find the software reliable, effective, and feature-dense. As consumers consistently have flawless experiences with Apple products and features, they promote them to others, increasing brand awareness and justifying high prices. Consequently, these consumers tend to be less price-sensitive, enabling Apple to set and maintain premium prices and have more price inelastic demand, increasing profitability. Since 2019, the average selling price (ASP) of Apple's iPhone and its global iPhone sales volume have increased by 23% (Tanner, 2024) (Curry, 2024). Apple's branding has impacted the entire smartphone market's wants and needs to be biased for higher perceived quality and price; furthermore, by 2029, the prices are further expected to rise by 15%, possibly resulting in more revenue for Apple if they can maintain expenses and volume (Tanner, 2024).

The four best-selling smartphones of 2024 were the premium-priced Apple iPhones; thus, consumers seem to prefer spending more on smartphones over more value-driven alternatives like Samsung, resulting in higher margins with greater profits for Apple (Knight, 2024). Apple has exploited their customers' wants and needs to mark up their devices and increase their profitability; specifically, the gross profit margins (GPM) to 45% which is dependent solely on their products' sales costs and revenue (Macrotrends, 2024a).

Brand judgements involve consumers' evaluations of the brand's quality, credibility, consideration, and superiority (Mchunu, 2023). **Brand feelings** refer to the emotional responses and attitudes consumers have from using the brand or being aware of it.

Apple developing the highest quality hardware and software for their devices makes them more reliable, consistent, and enjoyable. 84% of Apple users trust the brand to deliver high-quality products, and 76% enjoy the entire experience of purchasing Apple products, proving positive brand judgements (Lindler, 2024). These positive opinions improve brand judgements and increase customers' likelihood to purchase, increasing sales revenue. These feelings are vital to creating long-lasting relationships with the brand for returning customers. Apple's reputation for quality and groundbreaking innovation generates excitement and anticipation, creating a subconscious emotional bond for the brand, and increasing customer commitment (Apple, 2023). According to a study of over 1400 advertisement campaigns, marketing strategies and promotion with credibility and memorable emotions succeed twice as well (Decker, 2018). Consequently, Apple's advertising return on investment (ROI) would be very high; on average spending \$1.8 billion on advertising, and generating \$10.34 billion by displaying families and informal usage in their advertisements, a significantly successful method of promotion due to the creation of brand feelings and judgements which customers desire to resonate with (Parker, 2023) (Reuters, 2024).

Brand resonance refers to the most passionate level of consumers' active engagement, loyalty, community, and attachment to the brand, which has two dimensions: interactive activity and intensity (Mchunu, 2023).

Apple's powerful, integrated ecosystem development and branding result in the daily behavioural habits of customers who subconsciously require Apple products. This ecosystem results in customers' lives being dependent on and centred around Apple, which leads to

intense loyalty and brand-switching reluctance; being 21 times less likely to switch brands compared to Samsung owners (Adams, 2024). This would depend on the customers' satisfaction with the integrated technology, as it can lock customers to the brand for their whole lives, with 92% of iPhone owners sticking with Apple for their next purchase and 70% of iPhone users vowing to never switch to Android, increasing their CLV (Pawar, 2024) (Adams, 2024). From the existing, successful ecosystem, customers' interest in product launches would also be higher, with more sales in the introduction stage of product launches; 37 million iPhone 16 preorders bringing in over \$30 billion in revenue (Kuo, 2024). Simultaneously, Apple's profitable services revenue reaching an all-time high of \$100 billion indicates strong ecosystem loyalty. Customers are also willing to pay more to personalise their Apple experience to seamless perfection, further increasing their attachment to the brand as it becomes a vital part of their routine, lives and identity (Leswing, 2024).

The problem with analysing brand awareness is the bias and difficulty of quantifying concepts like salience at a scale concerning billions of people; therefore, making the process complex and subjective. However, using large data sets in secondary research of surveys reduces the effect of subjectivity.

Brand loyalty

Brand loyalty is when customers repeatedly and habitually buy the same brand. Apple consistently launches innovative products, maintains high design and quality standards, and creates engaging customer experiences. When trying to sell iPhones, Apple's approach is centred around incentivising consumers to upgrade and replace their existing devices, even if they don't have any technical problems; therefore, they focus their sales strategies on giving the customer a psychological upgrade. According to the Social Identity Theory, an individual's membership in social groups contributes significantly to their sense of self and

identity, which “provides a framework to explain intergroup behaviour” (Harwood, 2020). People tend to categorise themselves with others into different social groups, in this case, Apple, which impacts their opinions, actions, and loyalty (McLeod, 2023). The three factors of loyalty that I will analyse are social identity, ingroup favouritism, and self-esteem, which are vital to analyse the extent to which brand loyalty affects financial performance.

Apple has developed the most valuable brand worth over \$1 trillion of innovation, design, and status through minimalism and user-centricity, which creates a sense of belonging and pride among its customers, who see themselves as joining or being part of a premium group (Kantar, 2024). This consequently makes owning an iPhone more rewarding on a level more than functional but emotional, increasing customer retention rates by 20% above Apple’s closest competitor Samsung (Gitnux, 2021). Apple’s marketing emphasises creativity, especially with the ‘Shot on iPhone’ campaign and events, appealing to consumers who want to associate with these values and have the potential to do it themselves with Apple, incentivising loyalty, strengthening their social identity with the brand and creating a strong emotional link. These consumers act as social proof to potential customers and make them more likely to choose Apple as they believe others already enjoy it, resulting in lower customer acquisition costs, more sales and the cycle being repeated. However, this approach relies on maintaining a positive brand image; therefore, any damage to Apple’s brand perceptions can disrupt this cycle of consumer loyalty and act as a barrier to growth and financial success.

Most Apple users exhibit strong in-group favouritism, valuing Apple’s ecosystem highly due to the brand’s product design and innovation, and over the last 15 years, the global iPhone

user base has consistently increased to over 1.3 billion users as the preferred brand (Dean, 2024).

Figure 3: iPhone users worldwide (Dean, 2024)

Apple’s customer base’s loyalty is influenced by their desire to maintain a positive social image and status associated with Apple’s branding, causing self-enhancement; therefore, switching to ‘inferior brands’ like Samsung is seen as a downgrade in their identity. This is reflected by the fact that “81% of Apple customers feel a sense of pride and prestige in owning Apple products” (Lindler, 2024). This highlights the strong emotional bond that customers have with the brand, which would incentivise loyalty and purchases even if the market may have technologically superior products to Apple. However, these customers value the status associated with Apple, despite the premium cost and technical utility, allowing Apple to have a stable revenue stream in the technically advancing smartphone market.

The Net Promoter Score (NPS) is a tool that asks customers on a scale of 1 to 10 to rank how likely they are to recommend a brand to a friend. Apple’s NPS in 2023 was 61, while Samsung’s was significantly lower at 41 which indicates Apple’s customers’ satisfaction with the brand and their enthusiastic loyalty to support and advocate it (Qualtrics, 2024, Comparably, 2024a). Due to Apple’s sleek and premium design, their products are often

perceived as superior in comparison to Samsung's, being less desirable through appearance judgement, derogating Samsung and reinforcing customers' loyalty towards Apple (Molina, 2023). Apple's customers contribute to their success and brand identity, but Apple also contributes significantly to their customers' identities. The bi-directional loyalty and connection establish a very tight bond between Apple and its customers as it contributes to their identities and self-esteem, establishing recurring revenue streams and satisfied customers which in the long-run makes sales revenue more predictable and financial performance more economically sustainable even with potentially higher margins. In conclusion, Apple facilitates a sense of belonging in its customer base due to their premium product lines, resulting in 93% customer loyalty. Meanwhile, their competitor Samsung's alternate strategy; developing powerful technologies for all price ranges, which results in lower customer loyalty (Catsaros, 2023). However, the quantification of intangible brand loyalty comes with challenges due to its oversimplified definition and how different indicators don't translate directly to financial performance.

Brand development

Brand development is the continuous process of defining, refining, and testing the strategy of a brand (Tiller, 2024). The Brand Value Chain is a tool that categorises marketing processes' contribution to the development and value of a brand (EdrawMax, 2021). Goodwill represents a company's intangible assets which enhance the market value of the physical assets, such as reputation, employee dedication, customer relationships, and established networks (CFI, 2022).

Figure 4: Brand Value Chain (EdrawMax, 2021)

Marketing Program Investment

Marketing program investment refers to a company’s capital expenditure on communicating with customers in a market, focused on a product that is intended for mass commercialisation, with extensive research and design to ensure its success. Apple’s brand philosophy is centred around giving the customer a simple and seamless experience, apparent in all aspects of their marketing: product development, promotion and employee-customer relationships.

Apple’s products are the most important and relevant features that provide an aspect of differentiation in the market that customers first think about and are exposed to, which must align with the brand’s identity. Apple’s intuitive design features and USPs undergo countless research and testing to ensure that value multipliers such as the quality and relevance of the features are optimised. This process specifically reinforces Apple’s USPs, premium features and consequent market leadership in innovation as visible in the 2024 smartphone perceptual

map, which illustrates customer perceptions of brands. Consequently, these products contribute to better brand perceptions and product success in the market, increasing sales and brand relevance.

Figure 5: 2024 Smartphone brand perceptual map (Foster, 2023)

The communication of Apple’s values and products’ features is critical for succeeding in the hypercompetitive smartphone market. Apple’s main promotional method is obtaining a global focus on their product launch events, where they spend over a billion dollars annually, which equals approximately 1% of their annual profits (Basulto, 2018). Apple’s approach, combined with social media marketing, is to provide reminders of high-quality innovation rather than flooding consumers with advertisements, which proves more effective due to its enhanced, premium brand image and consequently high marketing ROI. Apple’s fundamental identity, established by Steve Jobs’ mission is: “The way we’re running the company, the product design, the advertising, it all comes down to this: Let’s make it simple. Really simple.” This contributes to the brand’s perception of sticking to their vision, and therefore being another point of differentiation; however, this approach requires constant innovation to maintain relevance in the smartphone market.

Apple's distribution strategy involves both online and offline channels, where in 2022, only 24% of U.S. iPhone sales originated from Apple stores (Marcom, 2024). 76% of sales being handled by third-party sellers also facilitates cost-saving by these sellers promoting on Apple's behalf, reducing expenses and increasing profits. This highlights the success of Apple's diversified sales channels and established business networks for a greater reach; however, the financial efficiency and necessity of the 530 global retail stores may appear impractical and rather act as liabilities.

Apple's stores are designed to illustrate the brand's cutting-edge innovation and minimalist simplicity, and labelling them as "Town Squares" reinforces Apple's narrative of developing a community as the Apple family. Apple stores, which include the "Genius Bar," as the "heart and soul" of its stores, aiming to deliver a unique and personalised shopping experience that reflects Apple's brand identity and originality. This strategy may be expensive in the short-run but can provide immense value in the long-run as it allows Apple to enhance customers' brand perception, reputation and relationships, which consequently increases the brand's goodwill. The investment by the general public would also increase from the current 37% ownership as the physical evidence of the stores would convince people directly exposed to them, positively affecting Apple's stock performance and market capitalisation (SimplyWallSt, 2025). However, Apple's profits allow them to offset the costs of their expensive stores, which have become so essential for their brand image that reducing the number of stores to cut expenses may even damage the brand's image and cause brand switching due to losing their iconic identity.

Figure 6: Apple Ownership Breakdown (SimplyWallSt, 2025)

Apple employees, referred to as “specialists”, play a critical role in shaping customers’ brand perceptions. These specialists’ extensive selection and training process picks out the most passionate and motivated employees who can enhance brand relationships and serve as 1:1 private sales representatives to make the customer sales experience more personal and warm. Apple’s recruitment process is centred around finding curious, devoted and empathetic specialists for “a career built on community” and ultimately adding perceptual and emotional value to Apple products (Apple Inc., 2024). Apple prioritising a service-oriented approach over maximising sales per interaction and minimising store expenses may not always align with financial objectives such as reaching profit-maximising output, particularly in highly competitive markets. However, the personal sales experiences enhance their brand culture, increase the likelihood of repeat purchases, and the long-term financial return of the customers’ lifetime value increases significantly. Additionally, this approach depends on a consistent, motivated workforce across all stores, and a decline in these standards could damage the sales experience and brand perceptions, decreasing the net positive financial impact of the Apple stores.

Brand Value

Market Performance

Brand value is an intangible asset that regards the expected earning potential of a brand, created by brand awareness, loyalty, and development. The market performance stage analyses success in creating brand value in terms of market share, price premiums, elasticity, market share, expansion, and profitability.

A price premium is a relation between the price of a brand's products and the market ASP, which is \$500 for the smartphone market (Taylor, 2024). iPhones are ~\$900, significantly higher than market averages, yet justifiable to consumers to keep purchasing because of their brand perception of high quality and ecosystem integration of all of their products working together seamlessly (Priday, 2023). Apple's 'Pro' versions further reinforce the brand's high-quality, exclusive elements, targeting professional segments. Apple uses decoy pricing of the middle-tier iPhones to sell more Pro models by creating a fear of missing out on the lower-priced options, driving up the ASP and leveraging higher profit margins of the Pro models. The value creation allows Apple to earn 82% of the smartphone market's profit share despite having 21% of the sales volume share and consequently sustain a high GPM of 45% (Richter, 2023) (Macrotrends, 2024a).

Apple's brand recognisability and credibility allow them to expand their ecosystem into complementary markets with their brand value to stand out and be customers' preferred choice due to the seamless integration; a branded experience at the centre of the Apple lifestyle. Apple's premium competitive edge protects them from price competition during expansion and allows them to maintain significantly higher profit margins while giving them extremely high growth potential through brand-enabled opportunities. In 2023, Apple's

paywall-blocked services generated \$85 billion in sales and \$60 billion in profit, due to the very low cost of sales and expenses of the intangible services, which act as profit drivers for additional revenue streams (Apple Inc., 2023). However, Apple's reliance on premium pricing and ecosystem locking may not guarantee future growth and profitability if consumer preferences shift, requiring a new approach and innovation.

Shareholder Value

The final stage looks at shareholder value through stock price, market capitalisation, and price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio. Apple has very low churn rates as their customers develop an emotional attachment to Apple's ecosystem, ensuring a steady, predictable revenue stream. Similarly, Apple's branding risk mitigation acts as a buffer for market volatility, stabilising financial fluctuations on profits. As Apple devices are premium products, in economic distortions, customers may first cut down on iPhone purchases as they aren't essential for their lives; however, Apple's brand can mitigate these effects by presenting their products as creative tools to make revenue, potentially increasing the demand at these times. This would act as an automatic stabiliser to keep the share price on a more stable growth trend, attracting more investment and increasing equity. Most evidently in the COVID-19 pandemic and recession, households' reliance on personal technology increased, resulting in Apple's share price growing at the fastest rate ever. While Apple's brand value alone cannot protect it from external factors that may affect shareholder value, their strong brand and ecosystem demonstrated how, even during the COVID-19 pandemic, the company could mitigate financial risks and sustain growth.

Figure 7: Apple stock price (Macrotrends, 2024a)

Apple’s brand value builds investor confidence, as it signals a strong value generation, consistency and low-risk profile, attracting more investment and boosting stock prices and market capitalisation to \$3.5 trillion (Apple Inc., 2024). The P/E ratio measures a company’s share price in comparison to its earnings. Technology companies usually have high P/E ratios of 20 due to their innovation-driven business strategies; however, Apple's P/E ratio is significantly more than the industry average at 35, highlighting their premium halo effect (Macrotrends, 2025). Apple’s products and brand being perceived as premium, consistent and pioneering results in more sales and consistency, increasing their P/E ratio as Apple’s shares guarantee stable growth and value gain. Consequently, the demand for Apple’s shares also increases, driving the P/E ratio further and this inflow of share capital allows Apple to invest more and benefit from economies of scale. This cycle, initiated by Apple’s brand value, further increases their tangible and intangible valuation, resulting in more sales and profit.

Brand value is crucial for Apple as it functions as persuasive proof both for customers and shareholders, allowing Apple’s intangible characteristics to be converted into more share capital and profits due to their brand image of innovation and stability. However, analysing and calculating the direct consequences of brand value isn’t objective because some

intangible assets' valuation can't be directly converted into financial assets without being affected by bias.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the extent to which Apple's financial performance is affected by branding is very high, as it appears that Apple utilises originality and credibility, which allows them to become the most sacred and valuable technology giant in the world. Apple builds **brand awareness** through innovation and elegant product design, growing their recognisability and reducing customer acquisition costs. Apple establishes **brand loyalty** among their customer base by listening to the market demands and meeting their personal needs to create a community that supports and relates to their technologies, increasing CLVs. Apple continues to invest in **brand development** to showcase their innovation and mentality to differentiate themselves from competitors, building a brand that successfully conveys emotions and offers satisfying USPs. Consequently, Apple creates **brand value** by combining the three aspects of intangible assets to grow as a company and, more importantly, a community, providing innovation to billions around the world and attracting investment to leverage further economies of scale.

Apple has achieved more success than their competitors due to premium brand positioning, emotional branding and marketing exclusivity. Other than branding efforts, this can also be a result of focused innovation targeting quality and ecosystem integration, convincing customers to purchase other products for the optimal experience and increasing retention for financial consistency by transforming the smartphone market's desires. On the other hand, Apple hasn't expanded their smartphone portfolio offering to serve all socio-economic groups like competitors such as Samsung, which have been increasing global connectivity with

value-driven devices of all prices. Facilitating technology accessibility has made Samsung the global leader in smartphone sales volume, especially in price-sensitive sub-markets.

Limitations

Due to the four aspects' intangible nature, analysing and comparing branding comes with subjectivity and inevitable reliance on biased data. This limitation is further compounded by the absence of primary information that directly quantifies the consequences of branding; however, even primary data cannot accurately value Apple's intangible brand assets. Nevertheless, this essay aims to establish the logical connection between Apple's branding and its financial performance by maximising the use of observable trends, theories, and real-world instances to demonstrate the broader and more certain consequences of branding on Apple's financial performance through different metrics and indicators.

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